

AN OVERVIEW OF IMPACT OF GST ON REAL ESTATE SECTOR IN INDIA

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Abstract:

Goods and Services Tax reform is one of the biggest reforms in the history of independent India. Goods and services Tax (GST) is an all-inclusive tax levied on producing, sales and utilization of products and services at a national level. The main objective of implementing GST is to avoid the duplication of taxes. The focus is on single nation single tax. The real estate sector is the most recognized sector globally. In India, real estate is the second-largest employment generating sector after agriculture. The real estate sector is growing at a rate of about 20% per annum and has been contributing about 5-6% to India's GDP. Real estate sector in India is expected to reach US\$ 1 trillion by 2030. The purpose of this research paper is to study the impact of GST on the Indian real estate sector and to overview the effect of indirect taxes on real estate sector in Pre and Post GST era.

Keywords: *Goods and Services Tax (GST), Real Estate, Indirect Tax System*

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INTRODUCTION

• Goods and service Tax

Goods and Services Tax reform is one of the biggest reforms in the history of independent India. Goods and services Tax (GST) is a inclusive tax levied on producing, sales and utilization of products and services at a national level. GST is a tax on goods and services where the tax liability is not only beard by the consumer but from the point of manufacturing of good or services to the point of delivering it to the final consumer all the manufactures, producers and retailers involved in it will also have to pay the tax. GST is introduced to over 150 countries across the world. In 1954

France was the first country to introduce GST. In India it came into force on 1st July 2017. Several countries have a unified GST system; whereas in our country a dual GST is projected i.e. central goods and services tax (CGST) and a state goods and services tax (SGST). The whole concept of GST for levying tax is based on 5 slabs 0%, 5%, 12%, 18% and 28%. GST removed duplication of tax (i.e. tax on tax) on the sale of goods and services which result in decrease the cost of goods and services. Activities like returns, refund registration response need to be done on the GST portal. This helps to speed up GST process.

- **Scenario of Real Estate Industries in India**

The Indian real estate (IRE) market is among the most recognized and reckless growing in the world. The real estate sector is growing at a rate of about 20% per annum Real estate and contributes round about 6 to 8 percent to India's Gross Domestic Product (GDP) and it stands second after agriculture in terms of employment generation. Since real estate sector was also loaded with various indirect taxes such as VAT, Service Tax, Excise, stamp duty and many more, it was brought under the horizon of GST. The real estate sector is the most known sector worldwide. In India, real estate is the second-largest employment generating sector after agriculture because it not only generates a high level of direct employment, but also it stimulates the demand round about 250 ancillary industries such as cement, steel, paint, bricks, building material, consumer durable and so on. Real estate sector in India is anticipated to reach US\$ 1 trillion till 2030.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

- Pinki, Supriya Kamma and Richa Verma (2014) studied and concluded that the new NDA govt. in India is positive towards implementation of GST and GST would result in a number of benefits for all the stakeholders involved, consumers, government at the central and state level
- Dani S (2016) a Research Paper on an Impact of Goods and Service Tax (GST) on Indian Economy stated that GST would impact negatively on the real estate market and due to GST there would be rise in cost of new house up to 8% and reduction in demand by about 12%.
- Niraj Dhar Dubey (2017), a Research Paper on "An Enquiry into the effect of GST on Real Estate Sector of India stated that after implementing GST there would be

Transparency in the taxation system in real estate and it will benefited both buyer and seller of the property,

- Rajkumar Kankariya (2019) a Research Paper on “ A Study of Impact of GST on Real Estate Sector in India illustrated that GST has significant impact on real estate as it has increased the cost of construction for the builders after its implementation. There was slowdown in the real estate sector after demonetization and implementation of GST.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

- To Overview the basic of GST
- To study the scenario of real estate sector in Pre and Post GST era
- To study the impact of GST on the stakeholder of real estate sector in India

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This paper is a descriptive study and purely based on secondary data which is collected from books, magazines, research articles and various online sites that provide relevant information on the study.

SCENARIO OF REAL ESTATE SECTOR IN PRE GST ERA.

In pre GST era, Central Government used to levy excise duty at the rate of 12.5% on most of the items required for construction activities. At the same time, State Governments used to charge value-added tax (‘VAT’) in the range of 12.5% to 14.5% on the same items. Earlier the taxes levied on real estate in the form of Excise and VAT on the construction items was not freely available as input tax credit against service tax i.e. 4.5% and State Specific VAT between 1% - 2% levied on the under-construction flat sold to the buyers.

The pre-GST taxability of Real Estate Transactions

Nature of Duty	Rate of Tax	When was tax required to be paid?
VAT	1 to 4%	On Sale of Under Construction Properties
Service Tax	4.50 %	
Registration Charges	0.5 to 1 %	
Stamp Duty Charges	5 to 7%	

SCENARIO OF REAL ESTATE SECTOR IN POST GST ERA.

After introduction of GST from 1 July 2017, there has been a important change on applicability of Indirect Taxes on the Real Estate Sector. Major relief provided to the construction companies in period from 1 July 2017 to 31 March 2019 through not

only allowing Input tax credit but also by providing single levy i.e. GST at the effective rate of 12% for Residential and commercial projects and 8% for affordable housing projects

Taxability of Real Estate Transactions under GST

Particulars	Applicability	Rate of Tax	ITC
On ready-to-move (RTM) properties for which completion certificates are issued	Not applicable - Because Sale of building is related as activity or transaction which shall be treated neither as a supply of good nor a supply of service as per SCHEDULE III of CGST Act, 2017	-	Not available
On under construction properties (For Home Purchased under CLSS)	Applicable as supply of services as per Schedule I of CGST Act, 2017	8%*	Available
On under construction properties (Other than above)	Applicable as supply of services as per Schedule I of CGST Act, 2017	12%	Available
On resale properties	Not applicable	-	Not available
On Land purchase and sale	Not applicable. As per Schedule III, sale of land is neither supply of goods nor services.	-	Not available
Works contract	Applicable	18%	Available
Composite supply of works contract	Applicable	18%	Available
Composite supply of works contract for affordable housing	Applicable	12%	Available

The homes bought under the Credit-Linked Subsidy Scheme (CLSS) draws 12% GST rate. The applicable rate is 8% after cutting the 1/3rd amount towards the cost of land. The developer have the option to opt for the old or new GST rate on projects in which constructions have commenced before 1st April 2019, However, for the projects which will start after 1st April 2019, the developer will have to opt for the new GST rate.

IMPACT OF GST IN REAL ESTATE SECTOR

- **Impact on Buyers** - Under the earlier tax structure, buyers required to pay VAT, Service tax, Registration charges & Stamp duty on the purchase of properties under construction. The price of properties was varied from state to state as VAT, Registration charges & Stamp duty were imposed and levied by the respective States on respective rate. Apart from these taxes developers also had to pay various duties like sales tax (CST), customs duty, Octroi etc. for which input credit was not at all available. On the other hand, under GST, a single tax rate of 12% is applicable on properties under construction while GST is not applicable on completed or ready to sell/move properties which result in reduction of prices for buyer under GST.
- **Impact on Developers / Builders / Contractors** – Before GST the developers required paid various taxes like Excise duty, VAT, Customs duty, Entry taxes etc. on inputs material and Service tax on various input services related to construction which result in rise the price of property and subsequently the burden of these taxes was transferred to the buyer.
After implementing GST, while there might not be any significant changes in the overall tax rates but the abolition of the tax on tax effect ultimately bring down the final cost of construction which help to bringing down the price of housing units and ultimately increase the real estate sales. This can be a positive impact of GST on real estate developers.
- **Impact of other Stakeholders** - The impact on the connected services like labour, material suppliers, service suppliers etc. influenced by the increase or decrease in the tax levied on these goods and services. This will have a substantial impact on real estate industry as a Whole. GST rates for some of the goods relating to the construction industry are given in below.

CONCLUSION

Application of GST has a major impact on the Real Estate Sector. While removal of cascading effect under GST as compared to pre-GST regime is beneficial to all the real estate companies. GST can be treated as simple tax system to work with as it has replaced all other prevailing Indirect taxes. This tax system aims at removing every possibility of cascading effect of taxes. It is expected to be a confidence booster for the Real Estate industry. It attracted the concern of buyer and investor by bringing more transparency in the taxation system. It benefited to both buyer and seller of the property.

There seems to be a bright future and a affirmative impact of GST on real estate developers on the whole. The government is trying its best to organize the country by creating transparency of tax in every industry including the real estate sector.

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